

THE ESSENCE OF ARTISTIC-IDEOLOGICAL CONTENT OF KHAREZMIAN EPIC

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Annotation: This article provides information about the theoretical features of Khorezm epics. There were also discussions about the possibilities of artistic and ideological education of middle school students through the Khorezm epic.

Keywords: Khorezm epics, middle school students, education, methodology, education system, pedagogy

The Uzbek Epic is very ancient and is a target of moderate spiritual heritage. Folk art, art occupy a special place in the spiritual maturation of a person. On the basis of the development of all arts, folk oral creativity stands. From the beginning of mankind to the present day, folk oral samples have been used in such types of art as literature, singing. The most beautiful type of these samples is the art of velvet. Art not only enriches the human worldview and thinking, but also begins it into the world of virtues, goodness, beauties. One cannot imagine life without singing. After all, art is one of the most important edges of human spiritual activity, a great and powerful force that encourages creativity.

In order to preserve and develop unique traditions of Uzbek bakhshism and epic art, to promote it widely, to strengthen the feelings of respect and attention to this art form in the hearts of the younger generation, to strengthen the bonds of friendship and brotherhood between different peoples, to further expand the scope of creative cooperation, cultural and spiritual relations internationally, president of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev, in this case, the need to organize creative meetings of scientists and practitioners of this field was determined among the festival events. In this regard, an international scientific conference was organized on the topic “the place of bakhshiqi art in World Civilization”. The main purpose of holding this scientific conference is to further develop the art of bakhshism and epic, scientific study of the epics of Uzbek and other peoples, scientific cooperation in this regard, as well as broadening cooperation in the field of culture and Arts in the field of education in the international community.

In the epics, very rich and ancient traditions of the artistic thinking of our people are embodied. Bakhshi is an artist, folk narrator, who sings songs and epics by heart, says, brings them from generation to generation. Bakhshi must have

mastered the folk marriage and culture, the history of the land in which he lived, and the art of hofism. He should be able to make good use of various forms of living folk language, word games and evils, folk proverbs and sayings. Being able to find a tone that frames the audience, making the saga attractive and interesting from the basic requirements of the saga telling. This in turn requires natural talent, strong perception, regular diligence and endurance training. Devotees love the motherland, love, friendship, brotherhood, courage and audacity, stories of diverse content that radiate heroism, are sung by Bakhshi.

KhorezmEpic has its own character in terms of repertoire composition. While solo performance dominates almost all the Lands of Uzbekistan in the delivery of epic works to El, in Khorezm, mainly collective performance leads. KhorezmEpic is characterized by its ancient roots, unique style and dialect, bright and attractive melodies. In ancient Khorezm, the epic Sayers were called Asik, Bakhshi, Goyan, women Khalfa. The word Bakhshi should be close to the Persian word from bakhsh. From bakhsh in Uzbek translates to “to dedicate”, “to forgive”. Indeed, the Bakhshi came to perform the epics dedicated to an event as if they were going through it, artistically.

The difference between Khorezm epic and other styles is characterized by its musicality, the wide development of song texts, the fluency of Khorezm epics as in most Turkic peoples, serjilo's instrumental prefaces, veiling and reverberatory changes. One of the rarest aspects is the unique style and dialect, the rich complex and, at the same time, the common literary and musical reality. In Khorezm performance ways “Go'ro'g'li”, “Avazxon”, “Baziryon” epics the songs and songs in the composition are no less than statuses or songs in terms of their potential. Khorezm Epic is composed of 2 major “Shirvanite” and “Iranian” schools. The common features of the two styles are that most Bakhshi are literally literate, and they do not invent poetry when it is their turn to sing after reciting a passage of the story, but instead use the epic in its place, memorizing its stable musical text. Sometimes his manuscript is carried by his side and can also be used during the performance.

Shirvani-style Bakhshis often keep it a secret to tell someone, even if they know well how to call the epic names. Those in the Iranian style sometimes go along with nomani's name throughout the story, where the text of the poem came from. Whereas shirvanite-style Bakhshis say dutor, bulomon, or ghijjak, epic in the circle, Iranian style Bakhshis perform the epic primarily with dutor. It also differs from Shirvani in its dramatic mungli character, simple musical weight, restrained execution and various sacrament movements.

One of the chief characteristics of the Iranian style epic tradition, Bakhshi mainly says a saga with dutor. He is often preceded by a Bullman or a vulture. In some cases, Bakhshi goes out to the crowd alone, with no musicians beside him, and sings the epic. The Khorezm School of Saga has its own tradition, distinct from other local schools of Saga. The Khorezm epics are characterized by their performance in "open voice", Sergio's instrumental introduction, curtain and reverberatory changes.

The contribution of Bakhshis to the development of Khorezm saga is significant, such as Ahmad Bakhshi, Qurbonnazar Abdullayev (Bola Bakhshi), Rozimbek Murodov, Qadir Bakhshi Jumaniyozov, Otahan Bakhshi Matyoqubov, Jumaboy Khudayberganov, Qalandar Bakhshi Normetov, Norbek Bakhshi Abdullaev. One of the people who created a unique bakhshiqi school in Khorezm is Qurbonnazar Abdullaev (Bola baxshi). Qurbonnazar Abdullaev "Avazxon", "Oshiq G'arib va Shohsanam", "Go'ro'g'li", "Bozirgon", "Xirmon dali", "Oshiq Mahmud", he knew about 40 epics by heart in total. Qurbonnazar Abdullayev (Bola Bakhshi) was given the title "people's narrator of Uzbekistan" in 1938. He was the first to be awarded such a title in Uzbekistan.

In conclusion, even if, passing by Times, the technique penetrates deeply into the lives of people, then still a person rests on national spirituality. Our folk art is the past, today and the future. This heritage, wise, great and immortal as our people, glorifies the Uzbek name everywhere and always. Because in the core of the original folklore works lies an idea that serves for human perfection. It reflects the immortal history of the people.

It serves to preserve and develop unique objects of this unique art, to promote it widely, to strengthen the feelings of respect and attention to this art form in the hearts of the younger generation, and to further strengthen international cultural ties between the peoples of the world. It is necessary to perfectly study the history of bakhshism and epic art, the work of Bakhshis and epics, conduct fundamental research in this regard, reconstruct uniting epics, and bring them to the future generation.

Recording Bakhshi performances on audio, video tapes is one of the main tasks in the development of epic schools, bringing their creativity to the state of the book, Making Khorezm sagas to note, making films at the level possible from these sagas. After all, epics that embody a few types of art, such as literature, poetry, music and spectacle, are not only a means of upbringing, but also a unique masterpiece of our cultural heritage.

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